

Interlayer Mediated Epitaxy of Cobalt Silicide on Silicon (100) from Low Temperature Chemical Vapor Deposition of Cobalt

Formation Mechanisms and Associated Properties

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This paper reports the development of a methodology for the growth of epitaxial CoSi₂ that uses Co films deposited by low temperature (390°C) chemical vapor deposition (CVD) from cobalt tricarbonyl nitrosyl [Co(CO)₃NO] as source precursor. This CVD process exploits the reaction kinetics associated with the adsorption and decomposition of Co(CO)₃NO on Si surfaces to ensure the *in situ*, sequential growth of an ultrathin interfacial oxide layer followed by a Co thin film in a single deposition step. It is demonstrated that this interlayer, consisting of a Si-O or a Co-Si-O phase, inhibits silicidation for uncapped CVD Co regardless of annealing times and temperatures. Instead, Co agglomeration is observed, with the degree of agglomeration being proportional to the annealing temperature. The agglomeration is due to a reduction in the overall energy of the system through decrease of the Co/substrate interfacial area. Alternatively, for Ti/TiN capped CVD Co samples, the interfacial layer appears to play a role similar to that observed for similar layers in interlayer mediated epitaxy (IME). This assessment is supported by the observation of epitaxial CoSi₂ for capped CVD Co samples after a single-step anneal at 725°C for 30 s. In contrast, Ti/TiN capped PVD Co samples annealed under identical processing conditions exhibited a polycrystalline CoSi₂ phase with a strong (200) texture. As such, the methodology presented herein represents a modified IME technique for the growth of high quality, epitaxial CoSi₂ films for applications in emerging microelectronics device technologies.

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Self-aligned silicide (salicide) processing is an essential component of modern microelectronics technology. In this respect, titanium silicide (TiSi₂) is considered as the most widely used silicide for salicide functions in logic devices.¹ Alternatively, tungsten silicide (WSi₂) is typically used for gate applications in dynamic random access memory products.² However, as device dimensions scale down, increasingly more stringent requirements are being placed on the properties and performance of silicides, leading to the need for new materials and process technologies.¹ Cobalt silicide (CoSi₂) meets these requirements, such as low resistivity, low Si consumption, and high thermal and chemical stability.³ Additionally, CoSi₂ provides the added advantage that its properties are independent of feature size and type of Si dopant.^{4,5} Furthermore, relatively simple modifications in the process flow can allow the formation of epitaxial CoSi₂. The latter is highly desirable given the sharpness of the epitaxial CoSi₂/Si interface, thus enabling the formation of silicided shallow junctions with low contact resistance and low leakage characteristics.⁶⁻⁸ Furthermore, agglomeration is dramatically reduced in the absence of grain boundaries resulting in superior thermal stability.⁹⁻¹¹

The epitaxial growth of CoSi₂ on Si(100) should be enabled by the close lattice match between the CoSi₂ and Si crystal matrices which exhibit only ~1.2% lattice mismatch.¹² Unfortunately, the achievement of CoSi₂ epitaxy on Si(100) is not possible in the two-stage approach typically employed to grow CoSi₂ on Si. The latter involves, in first stage, the deposition of pure Co on Si, typically by physical vapor deposition (PVD) means. This step is followed, in a second stage, by a thermally driven solid state reaction with the Si substrate to grown CoSi₂.^{12,13} In this case, an unrestricted supply of Co is available to the reaction process, with the rate limiting step being the formation of intermediate phases, primarily Co₂Si and CoSi, as a prelude to the growth of the CoSi₂ phase.¹³ These phases are not epitaxially matched to Si, leading ultimately to the growth of polycrystalline CoSi₂.¹³

Clearly, the realization of epitaxy requires the elimination of the intermediate phases discussed above. This condition is achievable when the supply rate of Co to the silicidation reaction is sufficiently slow to allow the formation of the disilicide and the occurrence of epitaxial alignment at the same time.¹³ One successful strategy to achieve this goal involves the insertion of an interfacial layer between Co and Si, a process commonly known as interlayer mediated epitaxy (IME). This method was first

demonstrated with a titanium interlayer, which was referred to as titanium interlayer mediated epitaxy (TIME).^{6,10,14-17} The typical TIME processing flow involves the *in situ*, sequential deposition of titanium then Co. Subsequent annealing causes the Co and titanium to first intermix around 300°C. Intermixing is followed by epitaxial growth of CoSi₂ at higher annealing temperature, with the titanium being driven to the surface of the resulting CoSi₂ phase.^{3,6,10,14-17}

In the TIME process, titanium acts both as an oxygen getterer, by removing interfacial native oxide and reaction barrier, by preventing the formation of the intermediate Co₂Si and CoSi phases. Both roles were believed to be equally crucial in the achievement of epitaxy.^{3,6,10} However, a number of authors have recently suggested that although oxygen gettering is important, the role of titanium as reaction barrier is actually the key to CoSi₂ epitaxy.^{8,18,19} For example, Selinder *et al.* showed that the presence of parts per million oxygen in the annealing gas was critical to CoSi₂ epitaxy. This behavior was attributed to the formation of a stable Co-Ti-O (spinel) membrane phase at the metal/Si interface.¹⁹ The absence of oxygen led to the growth of the intermediate CoSi phase, which was followed by the formation of polycrystalline CoSi₂.

Similarly, Tung reported the development of an oxide mediated epitaxy (OME) technique for epitaxial CoSi₂ formation.¹¹ The OME method involves the growth of a 0.5 to 1.5 nm thick, nonstoichiometric, SiO_x (x < 2) interfacial layer by submerging the Si substrate in either a boiling HCl:H₂O₂:H₂O = 3:1:1 solution for 5 min. or a hot (90°C) NH₄OH:H₂O₂:H₂O = 1:1:4 solution for 20 min. In both cases, high quality epitaxial CoSi₂ was formed after annealing of a subsequently deposited Co layer, 1 to 3 nm thick, at 500-700°C. Tung argued that the thin SiO_x layer acts as a diffusion barrier which delays the Co-Si reaction until the annealing temperature exceeds 500°C, thus inhibiting the formation of the intermediate Co₂Si and CoSi phases. Interestingly, Tung observed that a thicker (20 Å) stoichiometric SiO₂ interfacial layer was detrimental to CoSi₂ epitaxy, with the resulting CoSi₂ layer being nonuniform and exhibiting poor epi-taxial quality.¹¹ Other workers also reported the observation of epitaxial CoSi₂ when germanium²⁰ or tantalum²¹ are employed as interfacial barrier between Co and Si. Unlike traditional methods for epitaxial CoSi₂ growth, such as molecular beam epitaxy (MBE), the IME process is attractive because of its compatibility with standard complementary metal oxide semiconductor (CMOS) device fabrication flow. However, the introduction of a reaction barrier interlayer implies added process complexity because of the additional deposition and etching process steps required. Even though this is justified because of the significantly improved performance,^{3,6,7} it is still highly desirable to identify a modified IME technique for the *in situ*

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formation of the interfacial and co layers as one unified growth process.

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Various cobalt source precursors have already been investigated for the chemical vapor deposition (CVD) of Co for magneto-optics applications,^{22,23} magnetic Co-containing alloys,^{24,25} *in situ* doping with Co,^{26,27} and formation of epitaxial CoSi₂ for microelectronics device applications.²⁷⁻²⁹ Among all potential sources, considerable attention was dedicated to the source precursor dicobalt octacarbonyl, Co₂(CO)₈. A serious drawback for its usage is the existence of undesirable, yet thermodynamically favorable, polymerization and hydrogenation reactions that compete with the formation of pure Co.³⁰ It is also known to be unstable during storage, even under vacuum or inert atmosphere.³¹

Instead, prior work by the present investigators has identified cobalt tricarbonyl nitrosyl, Co(CO)₃NO, as a worthy manufacturing source for CVD Co.³² Its advantages include high vapor pressure (26 Torr at 0°C and 100 Torr at 25°C), availability in liquid form, and relatively good thermal stability during transport and handling. In addition, the existence of Co in zero oxidation state makes this precursor amenable to the clean breakage of metal-ligand bonds at low temperatures, leading to the deposition of pure Co.^{32,33} In this report, results are presented from the successful application of this CVD Co process, in combination with a sacrificial titanium/titanium nitride (Ti/TiN) layer, for the growth of high quality, epitaxial CoSi₂ films for applications in emerging CMOS device technologies.

Experimental

Cobalt films with thickness of 300 + 30 Å were deposited using thermal CVD from Co(CO)₃NO as source precursor. Specific process details were reported elsewhere.²⁰ Deposition was performed in a standard custom designed, stainless steel alpha-type CVD reactor using Si(100) substrates. The Si(100) substrates were subjected to a predeposition, *ex situ* organic chemical clean consisting of an acetone and methanol rinse. The native oxide was subsequently etched in a 10% hydrofluoric acid solution followed by a deionized (DI) water rinse. Finally, the samples were dried in a high-purity argon atmosphere. Additional substrates used were nonpatterned silicon dioxide (SiO₂) and silicon nitride (Si₃N₄) on Si. The SiO₂ and Si₃N₄ layers had a thickness of, respectively, 250 and 80 nm. Both substrates were exposed to the same *ex situ*, redeposition, organic cleaning described above. These samples served as control samples during our subsequent annealing studies. The purpose was to ensure that the thermal treatment steps did not result in undesirable interactions between Co and the typical spacer materials used in actual device structures.

CVD Co films were deposited using the optimized process window displayed in Table I. The resulting films were divided into two splits. These splits were subsequently processed and annealed as described below. All annealing studies were performed in an AG Associates Heatpulse model 610 single wafer rapid thermal processor (RTP). In a typical annealing experiment, the sample was placed on a 5 in. carrier sensor wafer equipped with a K-type thermocouple. The thermocouple was used to provide real-time measurements of sample temperature during actual annealing. The oven was then purged with ultrahigh purity nitrogen (99.999%) for 10 min prior to each annealing step. All anneals were carried out in the same nitrogen (N₂) atmosphere. The temperature ramp rate was approximately 40°C/s. At the end of the annealing step, the heating lamps were turned off, and the sample was exposed to a cooling rate of 70 to 120°C/min, depending on the annealing temperature. Cooling was carried out in the ultrahigh purity N₂ atmosphere.

The first split (CVD split I) of CVD Co/Si was left uncapped and was annealed without any additional processing steps. Alternatively, CVD split II was capped with an overlayer consisting of 12 nm thick TiN on 10 nm thick titanium. The Co films were not subjected to any cleaning prior to the capping layer deposition in order to avoid any chemical changes in the Co surface.

The Ti/TiN capping layers were deposited *in situ*, using collimated dc sputter deposition on a commercial Varian MB2-830 sputtering cluster tool. Base pressure prior to deposition was in the 10⁻⁹ Torr range. Titanium was deposited using a titanium target. Sputtering was performed at room temperature, 2 mTorr process pressure, 40 standard cubic centimeters per minute (sccm) argon sputtering gas, and 100 mm target to substrate. TiN deposition was carried out with the same titanium target, using 65 sccm N₂ reactant gas, 40 sccm argon sputtering gas, a process pressure of 4 mTorr, and

Table I. Typical process parameters for thermal CVD Co from Co(CO)₃NO.

Parameter	Value
Substrate temperature	390°C
Precursor flow rate	0.5 sccm
Hydrogen reactant flow rate	750 sccm
Process working pressure	1.5 Torr

water. Alternatively, for the capped Co samples, the titanium and TiN capping layers were selectively etched in a solution of 3 NH₄OH: 1 H₂O₂:2 H₂O. This was followed by the Co etch recipe described above.

Sputter-deposited, 30 ± 3 nm thick, Co films were annealed under the same experimental conditions used for the CVD Co and used as control samples in our silicidation studies. As in the case of the CVD Co samples, 2 splits of PVD Co were prepared. PVD split I was processed uncapped. PVD split II was capped with 12 nm thick TiN on 10 nm thick titanium.

Analytical Techniques

The electrical, compositional, and structural properties of all samples were thoroughly analyzed using Rutherford backscattering spectrometry (RBS), four-point resistivity probe, X-ray diffraction (XRD), nuclear reaction analysis (NRA) for hydrogen profiling, and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM), and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Resulting key CVD Co as-deposited film properties are presented in Table II.

Table II. Summary of CVD Co key film properties.

Property (measurement technique)	Value
Oxygen, carbons nitrogen (XPS)	All below 1 atom % (detection limits of XPS)
Thickness (RBS and SEM)	30 ± 3nm
Resistivity (four-point probe)	15 ± 1.5 μΩ cm
Structure (XRD)	hcp Co
RMS surface roughness (AFM)	~3.6 nm
Average surface grain size (AFM)	~70 nm

substrate to target spacing of 116 nm.

All splits were annealed at temperatures of 500, 550, 600, 650, 700, and 725°C. For each temperature, annealing was carried out for 30, 60, and 90 s. For the uncapped Co samples, unreacted Co metal from the annealed samples was removed by a 15 min etch in 10% nitric acid solution in deionized

Angle 2θ (Degrees)

Figure 1. XRD patterns collected at low angle incidence for uncapped CVD Co films: (a) as-deposited, (b) annealed at 500°C for 30 s, (c) annealed at 600°C for 30 s, and (d) annealed at 700°C for 30 s. No silicidation is detected. Instead, a transformation from hcp Co to fcc Co is observed upon annealing.